

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D6.5 — Report on identification and application of registries for FAIR data infrastructures

WP6 – FAIRification and provenance services

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable we describe the characteristics of registries that are FAIR by means of a common metadata model that enables interconnecting existing core registries and ontology services needed for implementing Findability and Interoperability in data and services. The focus of this report is on how registries can be designed, extended and/or implemented to better follow the FAIR principles, defining a number of characteristics to expose FAIR, machine actionable behaviour for the registry at three levels: the registry as an informational object or service, information about the registry, and the registry's machine actionable content. It presents two examples of applications that benefit from FAIR registries and discusses how the FAIR artefacts creating FAIR registries can be the basis for an interconnected network of FAIR resources.

Project Objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached/this deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a. Development of a personalized guidance to understanding and implementing the FAIR principles.
- b. Implementation of a common metadata model to interconnect existing core registries and ontology services needed for implementing Findability and Interoperability in data and services.**
- c. Developing common interoperable provenance standard. Provenance will enable machine readable description of history from biological material to data generation and data processing, in order to assess fitness for purpose and this reusability of data.
- d. Use the common provenance standard to support traceability of genetic material in order to implement support for Nagoya Protocol.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Introduction

The terms registry and repository have often been used interchangeably. However, in areas or communities where these terms are used separately, the term registry commonly refers to a service that contains information about resources, i.e., its metadata, and the term repository refers to a service that actually contains the resources, whatever the resources may be, e.g., datasets, container images, ontologies or articles.

In this document we adopt the latter approach by distinguishing registries and repositories, where registries contain metadata describing resources and repositories also contain the resources themselves. In this sense, registries serve as catalogues of metadata that describe resources that are located in repositories or other hosting infrastructure. The focus of this report is on registries and how they can be designed, extended and/or implemented to better follow the FAIR principles.

Another distinction that we use in this report is between FAIR-compliant and FAIR-enabling registries. The former refers to the degree to which the registry follows the FAIR principles, i.e., its own FAIRness. Examples of FAIR-compliant features include the registry having metadata about itself and the registry (in fact its metadata) being registered in a searchable resource so others can find the registry. The latter refers to features of registries that enable or facilitate the improvement in FAIRness of the objects made available through the registry. An example of FAIR-enabling feature of a registry is the adoption of community agreed metadata schemas to enable the metadata made available through the registry to fulfil the requirements of, for instance, FAIR principles R1.3 ((meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards) and F2 (data are described with rich metadata).

This report is further structured as follows: in section 2 we provide the historical content in which the work has been conducted. To define a set of guidelines for designing, extending, and developing FAIR-compliant registries, we analyse the FAIR principles and their impact on registries in section 3. From this analysis, we identify the main requirements for registries to better follow the FAIR principles in section 4. Based on these requirements, we define a number of characteristics for these types of applications to expose the expected FAIR behaviour. In section 5 we present a number of examples of applications to make use and benefit from FAIR registries. In section 6 we elaborate shortly how FAIR artefacts were used to implement the examples, and how the same artefacts can be used to build a functional network of connected FAIR resources, including registries.

2. History

The results described in this document are the outcome of Task 6.2 in EOSC-Life on the definition of FAIR registries that support FAIR ecosystems. To explain the role of FAIR registries, it was extended with examples of how FAIR registries could be used for ‘automated finding and using FAIR data in a FAIR registry’.

The main motivation for this work was to analyse common characteristics of registries against requirements derived from the FAIR principles. The hypothesis is that, by complying with these requirements, registries would become increasingly findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. This would bring benefits for the involved communities such as the ability of reusing content from various registries using similar approaches, protocols, interface, etc.

During the execution of Task 6.2 we identified the FAIR principles that are relevant for registries, registries' metadata, and registries' content (tables 1, 2 and 3 in section 3, respectively). Based on these identified principles, we derived the requirements that registries should satisfy to improve their FAIRness (section 4). The project's use cases were used as guidelines of what needed to be realised and as validation examples of the recommendations for FAIR registries.

Three example cases were explored within the EOSC-Life Task 6.2. The first case was inspired by observing the process of registering patient data in a European rare disease registry (EuRR-Bone) within the LUMC. This process takes place as part of collecting data for the patient registry of the European Reference Network of rare Bone Disease expert centres (ERN-BOND). Disease codes were manually recoded from the locally applied vocabulary (SNOMED) to the recommended vocabulary for European rare disease registries (codes linked to the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology ORDO), using ad hoc mapping tables. For EOSC-Life this case was translated into a ‘find and use’ case for machine actionable mappings and an automated workflow was developed to find and use machine actionable SNOMED-ORDO mappings (see section 5). Work in progress (not shown in this deliverable report, but see [10]), is an application of a similar approach to ‘find and use’ machine actionable workflows via WorkflowHub¹ and RO-Crate², two EOSC-Life related resources. Metadata provided by RO-Crate was used as the machine actionable metadata to find and use a workflow. The example workflow was the same as for the first use case. This work is planned to be continued in future projects. The third use case and second example in this report demonstrates using machine actionable FAIR registry metadata for finding and using the correct transcriptomics analysis method based on the machine actionable description of the type of transcriptome data (section 5). The original workflow was developed in the European Joint Programme Rare Diseases (EJP RD). This served as a substrate for Task 6.2 to create a proof-of-concept of ‘finding and using’ FAIR registry metadata to apply the correct omics analysis method. The workflow is used in the EJP RD project as a demonstration of ‘federated analysis on FAIR data’. Next versions of the workflow will be developed in the EJP RD.

Result	References	Contribution by Task 6.2 + relation to other projects
FAIR data point specifications and publications	[1], [5]	Task 6.2 contributed part of its effort to influence the specification and publication of the DCAT-based FAIR Data Point specification (FDP) and reference implementation. Thereby it contributed to the uptake of FDPs, especially in the EU rare disease domain where it is the minimal requirement for resources to join the federated ‘virtual platform’.
Extension of DCAT.	EOSC-Life 2 nd periodic report	Task 6.2 is the main responsible for creating an extension of DCAT for its use cases with classes for Registry, Repository, Workflow, and Mapping. It contributed to a collaboration with the EJP RD metadata working group for their extensions of DCAT. The EJP RD metadata model is a first level requirement for every resource joining the EJP RD ‘virtual platform’ network of FAIR resources.

¹ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

² <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

Requirements of FAIR registries	EOSC-Life Deliverables 1.2 ³ and 6.2 ⁴	Contributed the requirements of FAIR registries and prototype reference implementation.
Characteristics of FAIR registries	This report	Task 6.2 identified the applicable FAIR principles and provided explanations.
Workflows visualising automated finding and using mappings and workflows	[10]	Workflows were developed for Task 6.2 as example of 'finding and using' FAIR registries. Inspired by observations from various projects. The workflows are planned for use and extensions in at least the EJP RD.

3. Registries and the FAIR principles

One motivation argument for the FAIR principles is that humans and computational agents have different capabilities and, consequently, different challenges when dealing with digital objects. While humans have "an intuitive sense of 'semantics' because we are capable of identifying and interpreting a wide variety of contextual cues", computational agents are better equipped to operate "at the scope, scale and speed" necessary in the current digital object ecosystem. The envisioned scenario of the FAIR principles is one in which "machines are capable of autonomously and appropriately act when faced with the wide range of types, formats, and access-mechanisms/protocols that will be encountered during their self-guided exploration of the global data ecosystem". From this we can assume that machine-actionability is one of the qualities expected from the FAIR principles, and, for the purposes of this document is defined as "the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention".

The FAIR principles explicitly target both metadata and data, with data here being regarded as any digital resource, asset, or object (e.g., datasets, APIs, workflows, ontologies, models, and others). However, digital objects cannot be made FAIR without supporting infrastructure services that are FAIR themselves.

Many of the FAIR principles have the term "meta" in parentheses immediately before the word data. This means that the principle is applicable to both metadata and data (or other types of digital objects). Therefore, if we would like to consider only metadata by removing those parentheses, all FAIR principles address metadata. Moreover, since one of the main objectives of the FAIR principles is to improve machine actionability, it will not be achieved if metadata is not presented and made available in a machine-actionable way.

At this point we have two considerations, the FAIR characteristics of metadata and the FAIR characteristics of the data that can be acquired through their metadata. For instance, when looking at the data, the data usage license is normally expressed in the data's metadata. But when looking at the metadata, the metadata usage license is expressed by the metadata's metadata.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4432029>

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4705074>

Therefore, when considering the FAIR compliance of registries, we can focus on the registries themselves as types of digital services, on their metadata content or on the digital objects described by the metadata records contained in the registry (Figure 1). In this report we consider these three different but interrelated types of digital objects.

Figure 1: FAIR metadata layers giving access to metadata describing FAIR principles-compliant content in a FAIR principles compliant registry (top), a FAIR principles compliant repository (middle), and FAIR principles compliant resources (bottom). Blue arrows point at the digital object that the machine actionable metadata are describing and referring to. The cloud indicates that the descriptions are in terms of community standards for global machine actionable information from reference models outside of the registry. In a FAIR repository the digital objects are inside of the container; if the sources of the registry have implemented FAIR principles, then an index of FAIR metadata with pointers to the FAIR sources, conform to F1, suffices to deliver the expected behaviour of a FAIR registry.

In the following tables, we highlight the FAIR principles that are applicable to registries as services (table 1), the metadata of the registry itself (table 2) and to the content of the registries (table 3), i.e., the metadata of objects made available through a given registry.

When encountering a digital object such as a registry, a user or his/her computational agent would expect a certain degree of FAIRness of the object itself. The applicable FAIR principles to such objects are listed in table 1. In this table, we identify the principles that are applicable to this type of digital object, i.e., registries. Not registries' metadata but the registry itself as a computational service or informational object.

Table 1: FAIR principles related to registries.

Applicable FAIR principle	Comment
F1 - registry is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	To distinguish one registry from another, a globally unique and persistent identifier should be assigned for each registry.

F2 - registry is described with rich metadata	The discovery of a previously unknown registry can be done through properties of the registry such as name, description, license, etc.
A1 - registry is retrievable (accessible) by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol	The access to the registry should be made using a communication protocol that is standardized so others can also know how to access it.
A1.1 - the protocol is open, free and universally implementable	The specifications of the communication protocol used to access the registry should be open and free and the protocol should be implementable by whoever is interested.
A1.2 - the protocol allows for authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	In some situations, registries may need to impose access restrictions to some of its content. In these cases, the communication protocol should support authentication of users and authorization to some of its resources.
R1 - The registry is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	A number of accurate and relevant properties of the registry is used to richly describe it so others could better evaluate whether reusing it.
R1.1 - The registry is released with a clear and accessible usage license	It is important that the usage conditions of the registry are clearly and accessibly available through its usage license.
R1.2 - The registry is associated with detailed provenance	Part of the attributes that potential users of the registry use to evaluate whether to reuse if refers to the registry's provenance, e.g, creator, administrator, software version, etc.
R1.3 - The registry meets domain-relevant community standards	The reusability of services such as registries normally improves when these services adopt relevant standards defined by and for the communities they serve.

Table 2 below identifies the FAIR principles applicable to the information about the registries, i.e., the registries' metadata.

Table 2 - FAIR principles related to registries' metadata.

Applicable FAIR principle	Comment
F1 - registry's metadata are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	As informational entities by themselves, metadata should also be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
F2 - registry's metadata are described with rich metadata	In many cases it is relevant to have information about metadata records. In this case we are talking about the metadata of the metadata. For instance, we may want to know who created that metadata, when they were created, etc.
F3 - registry's metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the registry they describe	In order to guarantee that it is clear which registry is described by given metadata records, these metadata should clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the registry.
F4 - registry's metadata are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	The findability of a given registry is often effectively achieved when people or software applications use search engines to find it. To make this possible, information (metadata) about these registries should be included in search engines.
A1 - registry's metadata are retrievable (accessible) by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol	The access to the registry's metadata should be made using a communication protocol that is standardized so others can also know how to access it.
A1.1 - the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	The specifications of the communication protocol used to access the registry's metadata should be open and free and the protocol should be implementable by whoever is interested.

A1.2 - the protocol allows for authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	In some situations, registries may need to impose access restrictions to some of its metadata. In these cases, the communication protocol should support authentication of users and authorization to some of its resources.
I1 - registry's metadata use a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	The language with which the registry's metadata is represented should have a formal definition and the language specifications should be available for whoever is interested in learning about the language.
I2 - registry's metadata use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	The vocabularies that are used in the registry's metadata should also follow the FAIR principles, so these vocabularies are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
I3 - registry's metadata include qualified references to other (meta)data	The registry's metadata includes qualified references/links/relations to other metadata and data.
R1 - The registry's metadata is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	A number of accurate and relevant properties of the registry's metadata is used to richly describe it so others could better evaluate whether reusing it. This information can be considered as the metadata of the registry's metadata.
R1.1 - The registry's metadata is released with a clear and accessible usage license	It is important that the usage conditions of the registry's metadata are clearly and accessibly available through its usage license.
R1.2 - The registry's metadata is associated with detailed provenance	Part of the attributes that potential users of the registry's metadata use to evaluate whether to reuse if refers to the registry's metadata provenance, e.g, who create the registry metadata record, when, etc.

<p>R1.3 - The registry's metadata meets domain-relevant community standards</p>	<p>The reusability of the registry's metadata improves when adopt relevant standards defined by and for the communities they serve. For instance, the RE3Data schema for repositories can be considered as the basis for the registry's metadata schema.</p>
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Finally, table 3 identifies the FAIR principles applicable to the main content of registries, which is the metadata of objects registered in a given registry.

Table 3 - FAIR principles related to registries' content.

Applicable FAIR principle	Comment
<p>F1 - registry's content are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier</p>	<p>Each metadata record made available through the registry should be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.</p>
<p>F2 - registry's content are described with rich metadata</p>	<p>In many cases it is relevant to have information about the items comprising the content of a registry. Using the definition that registries contain only metadata, we are talking about the metadata of the metadata. For instance, we may want to know who created that metadata, when they were created, etc.</p>
<p>F3 - registry's content clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the registry they describe</p>	<p>In order to guarantee that it is clear which object is described by given metadata records, these metadata should clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the object they describe.</p>
<p>F4 - registry's content are registered or indexed in a searchable resource</p>	<p>The findability of objects described by the metadata made available in a registry is effectively achieved when people or software applications use search engines to find them. To make this possible, information (metadata) about these objects should be included in</p>

	search engines, possibly offered by the registry itself to control what is findable by whom under which conditions. FAIR principles do not enforce content to be unconditionally findable ('FAIR' is not 'Open').
A1 - registry's content are retrievable (accessible) by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol	The access to the metadata made available through a registry should be made using a communication protocol that is standardized so others can also know how to access it.
A1.1 - the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	The specifications of the communication protocol used to access the registry's metadata should be open and free and the protocol should be implementable by whoever is interested.
A1.2 - the protocol allows for authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	In some situations, registries may need to impose access restrictions to some of the metadata. In these cases, the communication protocol should support authentication of users and authorization to some of its resources.
I1 - registry's content use a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	The language with which the metadata made available through a registry are represented should have a formal definition and the language specifications should be available for whoever is interested in learning about the language.
I2 - registry's content use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	The vocabularies that are used in the metadata made available through a registry should also follow the FAIR principles so these vocabularies are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
I3 - registry's content include qualified references to other (meta)data	The metadata made available through a registry includes qualified

	references/links/relations to other metadata and data.
R1 - The registry's content is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	A number of accurate and relevant properties of the metadata made available through a registry is used to richly describe it so others could better evaluate whether reusing it. This information can be considered as the metadata of the registry's content.
R1.1 - The registry's content is released with a clear and accessible usage license	It is important that the usage conditions of the metadata made available through a registry are clearly and accessibly available through its usage license.
R1.2 - The registry's content is associated with detailed provenance	Part of the attributes that potential users of the metadata made available through a registry use to evaluate whether to reuse them refers to their provenance, e.g., who create the registry metadata record, when, etc.
R1.3 - The registry's content meets domain-relevant community standards	The reusability of the metadata made available through a registry improves when adopt relevant standards defined by and for the communities they serve. For instance, community agreements on metadata schemas for the metadata of commonly used types of objects.

4. Requirements for FAIR registries in data infrastructures

The FAIR requirements for data sets described in EOSC-Life deliverable 6.1⁵ are generally applicable to registries and repositories as well. In the preceding section of this report, we elaborated on these requirements by defining three levels of metadata for registries: (i) the content of the registry (metadata describing digital objects), (ii) metadata about this metadata, (iii) metadata about the registry (figure 1, from bottom to top). An additional requirement for registries pertains to functioning in automated applications. This requires communicating

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/3693883>

metadata between registries, and between registries and client applications such as search engines. Having machine understandable metadata *available* is necessary but not sufficient: protocols must be in place via which registries can be found by querying the metadata describing the registry (level 1), the metadata describing their content (level 2), and subsequently retrieving or analysing data objects by querying data objects' metadata (level 3).

To fulfil this requirement, we recommend that FAIR registries satisfy at least these criteria:

1. metadata can be retrieved using a common protocol,
2. metadata are made available in a commonly agreed presentation format,
3. metadata fields are put together in common schemas,
4. metadata fields use common definitions, i.e., related to concepts from commonly agreed ontologies/controlled vocabularies.

Section 5 presents examples of fulfilling these requirements by FAIR implementation choices. For instance, the FAIR Data Point Specifications [1] provide a means to implement a common metadata retrieval protocol via a REST API that navigates metadata in terms of the Data CATalog vocabulary version 2 (DCAT2 [2]) to navigate metadata and return results in terms of DCAT2 in the form of a serialisation of RDF [3] as presentation format (e.g. JSON-LD [4]), while DCAT2 itself provides a commonly agreed schema and common definitions [5]. The second example additionally proposes to use Phenopackets, a standard proposed by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health as presentation format and schema for genotype-phenotype data, as well as ISA, a set of tools to capture metadata on Investigations, Studies, and Assays, as a common schema and exchange format, and the Ontology of Biomedical Investigation for common definitions captured by ISA.

High level architectures can facilitate the interoperability of resources and registries according to the FAIR principles. In these architectures, registries (and repositories) containing FAIR data management artefacts, such as mappings and ontologies, can fulfil a special role in enabling FAIR-based ecosystems to form a global infrastructure.

5. Example applications of FAIR registries

The FAIR principles were conceived to facilitate automated, bonafide use of data. That means that a registry or repository that has implemented the FAIR principles for its content and for itself as container of that content (tables 1-3) should be automatically findable and usable. To explore this in practice we designed two demonstration cases of 'finding and using' machine actionable data in a machine actionable registry: (i) 'finding and using' machine actionable mappings via machine actionable metadata (section 5.1) and 'finding and using' machine actionable metadata of transcriptomics data sets in order to run an analysis method that fits the type of data (section 5.2).

Meeting the requirements of FAIR registries requires making implementation choices. Here, a general implementation choice was to define the metadata that describes a registry in terms of the W3C-recommended Data CATalog vocabulary (DCAT), version 2, augmented with Linked Data Platform (LDP) containment predicates to enable navigating DCAT metadata and an Application Programming Interface (API) to communicate with the metadata programmatically.

Figure 2: cartoon representation of ‘finding and using’ machine actionable content via machine actionable descriptions, here: mappings and workflows.

These choices conform to the ‘FAIR Data Point specification’, version 1.0 [1]. The FAIR Data Point specifications are proposed as a standard way to publish machine actionable metadata and communicate with it programmatically [5]. DCAT helps implement a number of the FAIR principles by capturing the description of a resource in a machine actionable ontology. It is widely used to facilitate interoperability among data catalogues. DCAT is built on top of existing vocabularies such as DCMI Metadata Terms [6] and the W3C-recommend provenance Ontology [7], by which I and R principles of FAIR can be addressed, and the Resource Description Framework (RDF) [3]. This basis ensures that DCAT is extensible by design. In the context of preparing the demonstration, it was extended with terms for ‘registry, repository, mapping, and workflow’.

5.1. Find and use machine understandable mappings via machine understandable metadata

The use case for this demonstration is a clinical data manager who would like to automate their workflow of mapping disease annotations in terms of a local standard (SNOMED CT [8]) to the standard required by European rare disease patient data registries (ORDO [9]). This is often carried out manually and may introduce erroneous and uncurated mappings, because existing mappings are difficult to find and use. Henceforth, our objective was to provide a ‘proof-of-concept’ demonstration that FAIR mappings in a FAIR registry can be *found and used* in an automated way.

We created a Taverna workflow to make the steps of the demonstration visible (figure 2)[10], and instantiated a FAIR Data Point (FDP) with a representation of a registry containing machine actionable mappings. These mappings were defined using the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM, [11]), with RDF as the underlying data model. A RDF file with SSSOM mappings between SNOMED terms to ORDO terms was generated via a SPARQL query on the Mondo Disease Ontology (Mondo, [12]) using RDFLib as a preparation for the demonstration [13]. We envision that communities will share mappings via established community authorities such as Orphanet in the rare disease domain, or FAIRsharing.org.

Figure 3: Visualisation in Taverna of the automated navigation of DCAT-structured metadata to find machine actionable mappings and then use them for automated queries. Starting with the FAIR Data Point URI (FAIR principle F1), the URIs of catalogues are fetched, then - following the DCAT hierarchy - those of mappings (a specific catalogue subtype), then those of distributions which provide the access URL to ultimately fetch the mapping file from the accessURL. The 'map_via_endpoint' is a script that queries the mapping file loaded into an RDF triple store to obtain ORDO codes for the input SNOMED codes.

Important is that these steps become increasingly automatable as more community-agreed, machine understandable standards are used to represent the semantics of metadata and data 'for machines'. Here, the data, the mapping file, is also machine actionable in a standard format (SSSOM represented in RDF), such that the automation can continue to the data record level. Although this is a relatively simple example, it shows how FAIR registries become more machine actionable by providing a mechanism to communicate with FAIR metadata (here by implementing the FDP specifications). In principle, using DCAT and RDF to define the semantics of a resource relieves the navigation algorithm of having to 'know' the content of the metadata upfront: DCAT metadata can be queried to find type information and URIs can be followed to obtain more information (see 5.2). The use of RDF guarantees that algorithms will find URIs.

5.2. Find transcriptome data type to use the appropriate transcriptome analysis

Our second example involves applying machine actionable metadata of registered transcriptomics data sets (Figure 3). The use case is a biomedical researcher who would like to extract differentially expressed genes from any number of transcriptomic data sets matching their topic of interest regardless of the transcriptome data generation platform. Without automation this would be very time consuming. The workflow template that we provide here is a FAIR extension of a workflow originally created for the analysis of Inclusion Body Myositis, a rare degenerative autoimmune disease, within the European Joint Programme Rare Diseases.

The workflow template was designed to demonstrate the use of transcriptome registries that provide metadata in terms of DCAT conform to the FAIR Data Point specifications (Figure 4). The

first steps in the workflow queries the metadata to find relevant data sets and retrieve their download URI by for instance type of data, studied disease, target tissue, and the study design. There are multiple ways by which this type of metadata could be linked to the DCAT vocabulary. A community-agreed ‘best practice’ has not yet emerged, but the X-Omics project provides useful guidance for combining DCAT with the ISA model (Investigation, Study, Assay) and GA4GH’s Phenopackets [14]. The workflow subsequently defines downloading the data using the download URL obtained from dcat:distribution, and then applying differential gene expression testing software. Which testing software is used depends on the metadata that can be obtained from the data sets: if ‘microarray’, then ‘Limma’; if ‘RNA-Seq’ then ‘DESeq2’. The machine actionable types can be defined using ISA and terms from the Ontology of Biomedical Investigations [15], in line with the X-Omics approach. Alternatively, dcat:resource could be further extended with terms for specific types of transcriptome data sets. In the final step of the template workflow results are aggregated using an algorithm such as Robust Rank Aggregation [16]. Many cases depend on the mapping of gene identifiers, which thus should also be described with metadata. Additional steps such as enrichment analysis can be added to the workflow as desired for biomedical research questions.

Figure 4 - Workflow template of metadata-steered differential gene expression analysis. The descriptions of transcriptomics data sets, expressed in DCAT, are queried via the FDP API (top middle), first to retrieve relevant data sets, then to extract the type of transcriptome data such that in the next step the appropriate analysis method can be applied.

6. Discussion

This deliverable described how FAIR principles can be applied to registries with content that aims to support FAIR data management. In most cases the requirements apply equally to registries ('content by reference') as to repositories ('content by value'). Moreover, they can also be applied 'at source', in which case registries need not provide much more than an integrated view of the results of a federated metadata query on the registered sources. The principles were applied to the registry (repository) as *the container* of FAIR content. It is trivial to see that for FAIR content to be used in an automated way, the container should also be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable for machines.

Two cases demonstrated the automated application that is possible if a registry (repository) meets FAIR requirements. Our observation is that many registries (repositories) that target the data management community provide functions for manual use via a website and a custom API for programmatic access. They may have additional metadata tags or markup such as from (bio)schemas.org to increase their findability in search engines. However, they often lack a standard way to communicate machine actionable metadata. The FAIR Data Point specifications propose such a standard mechanism. The current specifications propose DCAT, extended for specific catalogues where needed, Linked Data Platform predicates for navigation, and the RDF data model as the backbone 'language' for global machine actionability. Shape definitions specify additional constraints for validation [17]. Definitions in the Shape Constraint Language [18] are also used to generate a user interface in our reference implementation of the FDP specifications. Tooling is being developed to increase the uptake and utility of the FAIR Data Point specifications. This includes for instance a FAIR Data Point index that is itself a FAIR Data Point.

A project where this approach to 'FAIR metadata management' is being adopted is the European Joint Programme Rare Diseases. It defines a 'Virtual Platform Network' of FAIR resources. The minimal requirement to make a resource part of this network is that minimal metadata must be present in terms of an extended version of DCAT2 (fully backwards compatible with DCAT2 and defined in RDF) provisioned by an implementation of the FDP specifications. The Virtual Platform index of FAIR Data Points is a machine actionable catalogue of catalogues representing the network as a whole 'for machines'. New types of resources with new types of data can be added to the network through new DCAT extensions.

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Abbreviations

DCAT - Data Catalog Vocabulary

FAIR - Findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable for humans and machines

ORDO - Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology

RDF - Resource Description Framework

SNOMED - Systemized Nomenclature of Medicine

SSSOM - Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

